

Alternating Current Electrical Stimulation Effects in Human Dermal Fibroblasts

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ABSTRACT

Upon breaching of the skin an electric current is driven out from injuries by a potential difference held between epithelial layers; this current in turn generates an electric field (EF) in the vicinity of wounds. Surrounding epidermal cells can sense these endogenous EFs and respond with behaviours such as increased speed of migration, a critical factor for successful wound healing. Exogenous EFs applied via electrical stimulation (ES) can mimic the effects of endogenous EFs with improved results. However, optimal electrical parameters to enhance wound healing via ES have not yet been established. Moreover, while it is known that the outcome of an ES therapy is dependent on electrical configuration employed, the effects of alternating current have not been researched in the context of wound healing. This work explores the potential of alternating current for its use in ES therapies by evaluating its effects on a human dermal fibroblast wound model.

Key words: skin, electric fields, electrical stimulation, wound healing

1. INTRODUCTION

Injuries that disrupt the epidermis of the skin allow for the generation of an electric current driven by a potential difference held between epithelial layers (Barker et al., 1982); as a consequence, an endogenous electric field (EF) is established in the vicinity of wounds (Nuccitelli et al., 2008). The role of naturally occurring EFs in wound healing is critical as they are responsible for initiating and directing the wound healing process by guiding cell migration towards the wound (Zhao, 2009).

Application of exogenous EFs via electrical stimulation (ES) has been demonstrated to increase the speed of cell migration (Reid et al., 2005), accelerating wound closure; additionally, EF polarity has been shown to influence the direction of cell migration (Nishimura et al., 1996). For this reason, ES has drawn the attention of researchers around the world as a promising tool with potential for new developments and clinical applications (McCaig et al., 2005).

The mechanisms in which ES modulates the direction and speed of cell migration are still not fully understood. A currently accepted theory proposes that the effect of increased migration is a result of localised contractions of the cell cytoskeleton triggered by the accumulation of intracellular calcium ions (Mycielska and Djamgoz, 2004; Robinson, 1985), these contractions would

propel the cell in the direction opposite to the calcium concentration. The polarity of the applied electrical stimulus drives calcium ion flow towards the negative pole and thus modulation of the applied EF allows for directed cell migration. However, the responses of different cell types under exogenous EF application differ from each other, with some cell varieties showing increased rates of migration towards the anode (Zhao et al., 2011), others towards the cathode (Guo et al., 2015), and some even not displaying increased migratory speed at all (Yao et al., 2015). This exposes the necessity for further research in terms of both the functional responses of cells and tissues to ES and the mechanisms governing these behaviours.

Several studies have reported improved wound healing outcomes employing ES therapies (Nuccitelli, 2003); however, there is no consensus regarding what are the optimal stimulatory parameters to employ (Houghton, 2014). Although the benefits of ES have been demonstrated in practice, the response of cells to specific configurations and parameters is not defined; therefore, there is no basis for researchers and clinicians to follow while trying to select the most appropriate stimulatory parameters for specific therapies.

It is known that the outcome of a wound healing ES therapy can vary according to the chosen waveform (Reger et al., 1999). Direct current is the most commonly electrical stimuli employed in ES therapies,

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however, it can exert negative effects on patients. The electrochemical effect produced generates undesired waste products and burns (Behrens and Beinert, 2014), and it has also been reported to force intracellular toxin molecules into the tissues (Katelaris et al. 1987). Therefore, the main hypothesis motivating this research is that the use of alternating current may help alleviate the undesired negative effects associated with current ES modalities, evaluating the potential use of this waveform in wound healing therapies is thus required.

An experimental model was developed for the evaluation of the effects of electrical stimulatory parameters in cell cultures; this work represents the first systematic exploration of the wound healing-related effects of alternating current ES in human dermal fibroblasts; the outcome of this research aims to serve as a basis for further, more specific studies to be conducted, with the ultimate aim of profiling alternating current functional effects and determine its potential role on ES therapies. Further work will include different waveform and protocol configurations in order to conform a clearer picture of the properties of different ES modalities, ultimately aiding in the informed selection of waveforms and parameters according to specific therapeutic needs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Fibroblasts Culture

Normal human dermal fibroblasts were isolated from tissue biopsies of three different patients following their informed consent and with the approval of the Haydock Research Ethics Committee (16/NW/0736; approval date 11/11/16). Fibroblasts cultures were incubated at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Upon reaching 90% confluence, cells were subcultured, grown into passage 1, and further cryogenized. Before electrical stimulation (ES), cryogenized fibroblasts were thawed and plated in 6-well plates, with further incubation until they have reached 90% confluence. passage 2 fibroblasts were then used for all the experiments.

2.2. Electrical Stimulation

In order to prevent electric field (EF) fluctuations, a self-regulated voltage system was designed using a data acquisition board (National instruments; Austin, TX, US; cat. no. NI-USB6011) as the electric source. Software written in MATLAB coordinated the application of the electrical stimuli as well as the monitoring of the exogenous EF on samples. The

electrical stimuli were adjusted using a feedback loop in order to maintain constant EF intensities throughout the experiments. Silver/silver chloride electrodes were employed to transfer the electric charge. The electrodes were fabricated using 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes filled with an agarose-based conductive electrolyte gel and with silver wire pieces inserted as an interface between the electric source and the gel. A 6-well cell culture plate (Corning Inc.; Kennebunk, ME, USA; cat. no. 3516) served as the experimental chamber, with pairs of holes drilled on the lid over each well in order to attach the electrodes. Electrical stimulation was applied to fibroblast cultures for 12 hours using a selection of alternating current EF intensities in the physiological range (Nuccitelli et al., 2008) at 1 Hz.

2.3. In-Vitro Assays

This extended abstract details the methodology employed for two assays among those performed during the study.

2.3.1. Scratch Wound Healing Assay

A scratch assay was used to quantify cell migration. Briefly, fibroblast monolayers were mechanically scratched with a 20 µl sterile pipette tip before being exposed to ES. Microscope images were obtained immediately before and after ES. Fibroblasts that migrated into the scratched area were quantified using ImageJ, cells were included in the analyses if either the nucleus or at least about 80% of their cytoskeleton was observed to be inside the wounded area.

2.3.2. Resorufin Fluorescence Metabolic Activity Assay

Presto Blue Reagent (Invitrogen; Eugene, OR, USA; cat. no. A13261) was used to measure the metabolic activity of the fibroblast cultures. The assay was performed immediately upon ceasing ES and as per manufacturer instructions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Alternating Current Electrical Stimulation Effects on Cell Migration

Figure 1 shows the quantification of fibroblasts that migrated into the cell-free gap area during the scratch assay. Analysing electrical stimulation (ES) groups only, fibroblasts stimulated at an electric field (EF) intensity of 200 mV/mm experienced higher migration rates, presenting significantly more cells inside the wounded area by the end of the experiment than those at 25 ($p < .005$) and 50 mV/mm ($p < .01$). However, this enhanced migratory effect was overcome by the cytotoxic effect of alternating current, resulting in the control group showing the highest number of cells inside the denuded area. Stimulated groups were observed to lost up to 40% of their initial population, it is inferred that then control group showed the most quantity of cells migrating to the scratched area due to the sheer number of cells those samples contained in comparison with ES groups. When comparing ES groups individually against the control group, all of them presented significantly less cells inside the denuded area ($p < .005$) except for the 200 mV/mm group where that difference was not significant. The statistical significance between the groups was determined by one-way univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA), $p < .005$.

Figure 1. Quantification of cells that migrated inside the wounded area during the scratch assay. Quantification of cells that migrated inside the wounded area during the scratch assay. Alternating current electrical stimulation was shown to slightly increase the rates of migration in primary normal human dermal fibroblasts, however, this was overcome by the cytotoxic effect of alternating current. Values are given as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 12$). The statistical significance difference between the groups was determined by one-way univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA) $p < .001$.

3.2. Alternating Current Electrical Stimulation Effect on Metabolic Activity

Alternating current ES increased metabolic activity in primary normal human dermal fibroblasts according to a Presto Blue assay. Figure 2 shows resorufin fluorescence intensity measured from fibroblasts cultures upon ceasing ES. The data does not present any significant difference between all groups ($p > .2$) as determined by a one-way ANOVA. Considering that samples subjected to higher EF intensities contained significantly less cells. Those cultures subjected at 200 mV/mm had lost the most fibroblasts, with an estimated reduction of 40% from the initial population. Since resorufin is only metabolised by living cells it is inferred that alternating current can induce increments in cell metabolism in human dermal fibroblasts.

Figure 2. Cell metabolic activity as evaluated by a resorufin fluorescence intensity assay. Metabolic activity as evaluated by a resorufin fluorescence intensity assay. Primary normal human dermal fibroblasts showed increased metabolic activity when subjected to alternating current electrical stimulation, with higher electric field magnitudes inducing a more pronounced response. Values are given as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 6$). The statistical significance difference between the groups was determined by one-way univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA) $p > .2$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental in-vitro model for exogenous electric field application to cell monolayers under controlled conditions was developed. The aim was to explore and evaluate novel electrical stimulation (ES) parameters in

the search for potential novel methodologies to deliver electrical stimuli that could improve current wound healing therapies. This study represents the first systematic exploration of wound healing-related effects of alternating current ES on primary normal human dermal fibroblasts. More research is required in order to assess the potential application of this waveform in wound healing therapies.

5. FUTURE WORK

It has been inferred from our data that alternating current can induce increased migration speed in human dermal fibroblasts, this effect however, was overcome by the cytotoxicity of the treatment. It is known that stimulation time increases cytotoxicity and for this reason further work will be focused on new protocols which provide with the less or none cytotoxic effect while eliciting the greatest increases in migration speed. It has also been observed that apoptosis was not triggered, and cell cycle remained unaltered after electrical stimulation (data not shown), suggesting that alternating current electrical stimulation should still be considered as a potential waveform to use in wound healing therapies and that further research is therefore necessary.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the National Council of Science and Technology of Mexico (CONACyT) and the School of Materials at the University of Manchester for providing the financial support required to undertake this work with the scholarship no. 424671 and the Materials Bursary Award, respectively

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